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“FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL LIPSTICK CONTAINING ANTIFUNGAL AGENT”

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ABSTRACT

Cosmetics are incredible in demand since historical time till day. Lipstick formulations are most widely used to enhance the beauty of lips and add glamour to touch to the makeup. With this aim and objectives, an attempt was made to formulate herbal lipstick using natural ingredients. The natural drug used in the formulation is a curcumin which is used for antifungal therapy and Pomegranate arils extract is used as coloring agent. Preformulation studies revealed that API and excipients were found compatible for the formulation of herbal lipstick. Preliminary trials were carried out for determination of concentration of ingredients and drug. Two ingredients such as carnauba wax and cocoa butter was varied and remaining all ingredients was kept constant on the basis of preliminary trials. Evaluation test like melting point, pH, breaking point, thixotropy structure, softening point, solubility, permeability study was performed, and select optimized batch on the basis of evaluation of lipstick. Determination of curcumin antifungal activity and stability study was performed on the finalized formulation. Skin has to bear various external traumas like irritation, cheilitis, braking of lips, blacking of lips etc. as well as topical fungal infection. Attempt was also made to access the antifungal activity of the formulation against *Candida albicans*. Due to various adverse effects of available synthetic preparations and to improve patient compliance the present work was conceived by us to formulate herbal lipstick having antifungal activity to treat lips fungal infection and having minimal or no side effects which will extensively use by the women of our communities with great surety.

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INTRODUCTION

Cosmetics:

Cosmetics are the substances to enhance or protect the beauty of the human body dates back to vedic and puranic period. Earlier human race of tribal era used animal parts, vegetable leaves, flowers, color stones, shells, etc. to adorn their bodies. As per FD&C Act cosmetics are defined as "articles intended to be rubbed, poured, sprinkled, or sprayed on, introduced into, or otherwise applied to the human body for cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness, or altering the appearance." Cosmetic include skin care, creams, lotions, powders, perfumes, lipsticks, finger nail polishes, eye and facial makeup, hair colors, deodorants, baby products, bath oils, and many other types of products. It does not include soap. [1,2]

Cosmeceuticals:

Cosmeceuticals are cosmetic pharmaceutical products intended to improve the health and beauty of the skin by improve the health and beauty of the skin by providing a specific result, ranging from acne-control and anti-wrinkle effects, to sun protection. The concept discovered by Dr. Albert Klingman states that the Cosmeceuticals are topical agents that are distributed across broad spectrum of materials, laying somewhere between pure cosmetics (lipstick and rouge) and pure drug (antibiotics, corticosteroids). Cosmeceuticals, are the combination of biologically active ingredients which have medicinal or drug-like benefits and cosmetics which helps for beautification of the skin. Cosmeceuticals are topical formulation containing active ingredients that affects the biological function of the skin. External factors like air pollution, exposure to radiation from the sun and normal process of aging causes damages to integral components of skin like DNA, collagen and cellular membranes. Most of Cosmeceuticals uses vitamin, herbs, various oils and botanical extract. Desirable features of cosmeceutical agents are efficacy, safety, formulation stability and novelty. [2,3]

Herbal Lipstick:

Rational of the present study was to formulate the lipstick formulation for treatment of fungal lips infection such as angular cheilitis. Formulation prepared by using natural antifungal agent and coloring agent such as curcumin and pomegranate arils extract. Curcumin having yellow color and pomegranate arils extract having faint pink color, hence, combination of both gives dark color formulation. It gives moisturizer effect on lips and these possibly reduce side effects & cost of lipstick.

The aim of the work was to formulate and evaluate a herbal lipstick containing natural antifungal natural agent (Curcumin) To evaluate the lipstick for various parameters. To minimize adverse effects, drug interaction and increased patient compliance. Lipstick formulations are most widely used to enhance the beauty of lips and to add glamour touch to the makeup. Lipsticks are cosmetic formulations for the modification or accentuation of lip color and are prepared by molding a dispersion of colors in a waxy base, in the form of stick/crayon. Any preparations used in beauty treatments for lip make-up also known as sticks or more commonly known in beauty treatments by the name of lipsticks. When these preparations contain herbal ingredients, they are also known as herbal lipsticks. [4]

Different Lip Problems:

Lip problems include lip dryness, cracking, pain, numbness, sores and swelling. There are many causes of lip symptoms; they range from mild to serious. The duration and course of lip symptoms vary widely, depending on the cause. Lip Problems occurs as a result of injury, such as biting lips, burning them with hot food. Even a common infection can cause lip symptoms. Diseases or conditions that affect the nerves and muscles, including nerve damage or neuropathy, can be associated with symptoms that involve the lips. Lip symptoms may also be the result of cold and dry weather, infection, nutritional deficiencies, or medication side effects. Suitable drug candidates for medicated lipsticks are locally acting on the lips, soothing, anti-irritant agent, skin protectant, keratolytic agent, steroids, antibiotics, and anti-inflammatory agent. [5,6, 7]

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Selection of material

The various herbs such as curcumin and pomegranate used in the formulation of herbal lipstick were selected on the basis of literature survey.

Collection of material

The pomegranate fruit used in formulation of herbal lipstick was collected in month of January 2017 from the Chinchwad local market and the curcumin was used as antifungal agent in preparation of herbal lipstick was collected from the Nisarga biotech, Maharashtra.

Preformulation studies

Preformulation studies were the important and it was first step. The purposes of preformulation studies were to develop a collection of evidence about antifungal agent, coloring agent & on the basis of this information develop new formulation. Preformulation studies were done to examine physical and chemical properties of API and coloring agent and API when mixed with excipients.

The following preformulation studies were performed in curcumin, pomegranate extract and other excipients.

Preformulation study of Curcumin

Characterization of Curcumin

Drug-excipient compatibility studies

Characterization of Curcumin

Physical appearance

Sample of curcumin was visualized for colour.

Melting Point

The melting point of curcumin was measured using capillary method, the capillary was filled by pinch of curcumin and kept in the capillary apparatus and firstly observed the point at which product was started melted. After sometimes observed product was completely melted.

Absorbance Maxima

Solution of curcumin was prepared in methanol. Absorbance maxima were determined by analyzing this solution using UV-Visible Spectrophotometer in the range of 200-800nm.

Solubility studies

For solubility, equivalent amount of the drug was taken in different test tubes containing the different solvents. After the addition of each portion of solvent, Test tubes were shaken vigorously and then observed by visual inspection.

Calibration Curve

Stock solution of curcumin was prepared in buffer 7.4 methanol. From stock solution different diluted solution in concentration range of 1-6 μ g/ml were prepared. The absorbance of each solution was measured at λ_{max} 420nm using diluent as a blank and standard curve was plotted between concentration (μ g/ml) on X-axis and absorbance on Y-axis.

FTIR of Curcumin

FTIR spectra of standard drug were obtained on Brook α FTIR Model- Spectrum RX 1 spectrometer.

Drug-excipients compatibility study

A successful formulation of a stable and effective solid dosage form depends on careful selection of excipients. Therefore drug-excipient compatibility study was performed. The spectra of bees wax, cocoa butter, carnauba wax, cocoa butter and mixture of drug and excipients was determined by using Brook α FTIR Model- Spectrum RX 1 spectrometer. Any changes in the chemical composition after combining with the excipients were investigated with IR spectral analysis.

Preformulation study of Pomegranate extract

Characterization of the pomegranate extract

Physical appearance

Sample of Pomegranate extracts color pigment were visualized for color.

Melting point

The melting point of pomegranate color pigment was measured using capillary method, the capillary was filled and kept in the capillary apparatus and firstly observed the point at which product was started melted. After sometimes observed product was completely melted.

Determination of solubility

Solubility of Pomegranate color pigment was determined in distilled water, acetone, methanol, and ethanol.

Acidity test

The acidity test was performed by measuring pH of color pigment extracts.

Determination of λ max of pomegranate extract

Solution of pomegranate was prepared in methanol .Absorbance maxima were determined by analyzing this solution using UV-Visible Spectrophotometer in the range of 400-800nm.

Formulation of Herbal lipstick (HL)**Table 1: Formulation of Herbal lipsticks (HL).**

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Quantity (%)								
		HL ₁	HL ₂	HL ₃	HL ₄	HL ₅	HL ₆	HL ₇	HL ₈	HL ₉
1	Bees wax	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
2	Carnauba wax	5	5	5	3	3	3	2	2	2
3	Cocoa butter	45	46	47	45	46	47	45	46	47
4	Lanolin	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
5	Curcumin	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
6	Pomegranate extract	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
7	Olive oil	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
8	Rose oil	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
9	Lemon oil	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Evaluation Test for Herbal lipsticks [2, 8, 9]**Drug content**

Drug content of formulation HL₁ to was determined by (100 mg) of lipstick formulations was taken in 100 ml volumetric flask containing 20ml of methanol The resultant solution was filtered through membrane filter. The absorbance of the solution was measured spectrophotometrically at 420nm using methanol as reference solution.

Melting point

The melting point of formulated lipstick was determined by capillary tube method, the capillary was filled and kept in the melting point apparatus and it was observed that the product completely melted at particular temperature. This procedure is repeated 3 times and mean was taken as a final parameter. Generally, ideal lipstick formulations should have melting point between 40°C-55°C.

pH Parameters

The pH of formulated herbal lipsticks was determined using pH meter.1 g of lipstick was dissolved in 100 ml of distilled water and measured for its pH.

Breaking point

Breaking point was done to determine the strength of lipstick. The lipstick was held horizontally in a socket 1/2 inch away from the edge of support. The weight was gradually increase by a specific value (10 gm) at specific interval of 30 second and weight at which the lipstick breaks was considered as the breaking point.

Fig.1: Breaking point.**Thixotropic character**

This test was gives an indication of thixotropic quality and is done by using penetrometer. A standard needle of specific diameter is allowed to penetrate for 5 seconds under a 50gm load at 25°C. The lipstick was kept at 25°C prior to the experiment. The depth of penetration was a measurement of thixotropic structure. Penetration below 10 mm was inductive of soft and thixotropic structure. A product of high droop point with soft, thixotropic structure will assure good application characteristics.

Fig.2: Thixotropic character.

Solubility test

The formulated herbal lipstick was dissolved in various solvents to observe the solubility.

Softening Point

The lipstick sample was inserted in to an aluminum ring. Extra mass above and below the orifice was removed using a sharp blade to get a lipstick tablet in to the ring. This was placed in a refrigerator (6°C) for 10 min. After removing it from the refrigerator, the ring was fastened onto a stand. This assembly was dipped in to a beaker full of water. This was heated with a continuous stirring. Temperature was monitored using a thermometer. Softening point was the temperature at which the lipstick mass was loosened and falls to the bottom of the beaker.

Permeability Study

Cellophane membrane was soaked in and allowed to evaporate ethanol buffer (7.4pH) for 24 hr. 50 mg of lipstick mass was applied on the membrane and it was placed on the diffusion cell. Buffer (6.4pH) was used as receptor media. This was magnetically stirred (600rpm). The experimental temperature was maintained at 32°C by circulation thermostatic water inside the cell jacket. Sampling was done at 1hr interval and analyzed under UV at 420nm for 6 hrs.

Stability Studies

The lipsticks were placed for stability studies at room temperature, refrigerator and $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}/75 \pm 5\% \text{RH}$ and were observed for any physical changes.

Antifungal activity

Curcumin is fungi static .It act on *C. albicans* cell membrane. Curcumin interact with ergosterol containing cell membrane of *C. albicans* and causing cell wall disruption. The antifungal activity of curcumin from the formulation as well as from standard (Curcumin 0.064mg in 1ml Dimethyl sulfoxide) was determined using *Candida albicans* as a representative fungus, adopting the cup plate method. The antifungal activity was determined from the formation of inhibition zone.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterization of Curcumin and Pomegranate extract

Table 2: Characterization of Curcumin and Pomegranate extract.

Sr. No.	Identification study	Observed result	
		Curcumin	Pomegranate extract
1	Physical appearance	Bright yellow color powder	Pink, red oily pasty mass
2	Melting point	182° -184°C	136-148°C
3	Determination of solubility	Partially soluble in distilled water, soluble in methanol, ethanol, dimethyl sulfoxide and oil soluble.	Soluble in acetone, methanol, ethanol.
4	Determination of maximum wavelength	420 nm	482nm
5	pH	-	3.8

Absorbance maxima of curcumin:

The absorbance maxima of curcumin were determined by UV spectrophotometer and were 420 nm that is similar with the standard absorbance. (Fig.3).

Fig.3: Maximum wavelength of curcumin.

Calibration Curve

Table 3: Calibration curve of Curcumin in methanol.

Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
0	0
1	0.152 \pm 0.03
2	0.304 \pm 0.02
3	0.455 \pm 0.1
4	0.609 \pm 0.05
5	0.75 \pm 0.04
6	0.909 \pm 0.02

Fig.4: Standard calibration curve of curcumin.

FTIR of Curcumin

Identification of pure drug: It was carried out by FTIR spectroscopy

Fig.5: FTIR Spectra of Curcumin.

Table 4: IR Spectra having wave number range which shows signal assignment.

Sr. No.	Peaks observed(cm-1)	Group interpreted
1	3509.49	OH bending
2	1625.31	C-C and C-O bending
3	1503.17	C-O stretching
4	1275.05	C-O (enol)bending
5	1024.23	C-O-C bending
6	958.34	Aromatic trans –CH stretching
7	715.48	Aromatic cis –CH stretching

The drug sample was firstly analyzed by Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) with standard sample. The result indicated that Curcumin was pure and free from impurities because the value of drug sample similar with standard value.

Drug - Excipient Compatibility Studies FTIR of Bees wax

Fig.6: FTIR of Bees wax.

FTIR of Carnauba wax

Fig.7: FTIR of Carnauba wax.

FTIR of Cocoa butter

Fig.8: FTIR of Cocoa butter.

FTIR of Lanolin

Fig.9: FTIR of Lanolin.

FTIR spectra for mixture of Bees wax, Carnuaba wax, Lanolin, Cocoa butter and Curcumin.

Fig.10: FTIR spectra for mixture.

Table 5: Peaks and principal groups present in FTIR spectra of Curcumin, Bees wax, Carnuaba wax, Lanolin, Cocoa butter and its mixture.

Sr. No.	Observed peaks(cm-1)						Interpretation of chemical group
	Curcumin	Bees wax	Carnuaba wax	Cocoa butter	Lanolin	Mixture	
1	3509.49	3619.00	3315.52	3602.37	3372.87	3614.28	OH Stretching
2		2848.23	2848.19	2851.12	2873.94	2869.42	CH ₂ stretching
3	1625.31					1630.90	C-C and C-O Bending
4		1704.76	1737.7	1730.59	1723.98	1708.05	C=O ester stretching
5		2915.46	2915.87	2915.54		2937.89	C-H stretching
6	1275.17					1272.84	C-O (enol)bending
7	1024.05					1028.72	C-O-C stretching
8	958.34					931.54	Aromatic trans -CH stretching
9	713.48	722.37	720.22	718.39		761.70	Aromatic cis -CH stretching

Evaluation of Herbal lipstick

Table 6: Evaluation Test for Herbal lipsticks (HL).

Test	Quantity (%)								
	HL ₁	HL ₂	HL ₃	HL ₄	HL ₅	HL ₆	HL ₇	HL ₈	HL ₉
Drug content (%)	93.2±0.12	94.3±0.32	93.5±0.1	94.1±0.40	95.2±0.1	96.4±0.1	95.6±0.22	96.4±0.15	96.6±0.32
Melting point(°C)	73-76.2	71.8-74.6	69 - 72	66.3 - 69.8	61.4-63.1	58.7-61	56.9- 59.	49.5- 53	49.5- 53
pH parameter	6.8-6.9	6.7- 6.8	6.6-6.7	6.7-6.8	6.8-6.9	6.6-6.8	6.6-6.7	6.5-6.6	6.4-6.5
Solubility	CH ₃								
Softening point(°C)	70.3±0.0	68.5±0.07	66.7±0.05	64.6±0.03	61±0.1	58±0.4	56.9±0.01	53.7±0.03	46.5±0.05
Breaking point (gm)	106.57±5.72	98±3.41	95.32±10.6	90.43±5.74	88.76±5.71	83±4.21	71.74±3.62	64.51±1.17	55±5.30
Thixotropy (mm)	14.2±0.02	14.5±0.05	14.7±0.01	12.4±0.04	12.1±0.0	12±0.02	10.9±0.05	10.7±0.01	9.9±0.03
Permiability study(%Drug release after 6h)	11.86±0.1	12.28±0.12	12.71±0.06	14.22±4	15.46±0.08	16.12±0.12	17.14±0.10	17.56±0.1	18.42±0.02

Fig.11: Drug release profile of different formulations.

Selection of optimized batch

HL₉ batch was found to be good melting point, pH, and breaking point, thixotropy structure, softening point and drug release (%) than other batches.

Fig.12: Herbal lipstick (HL₉).

Breaking point of HL₉ batch

Fig.13: HL₉ Breaking point.

Thixotropy of HL₉ batch

Fig.14:HL₉-Thixotropy character.

Stability Study of HL₉ batch

The lipsticks (HL₉) were placed in three different stability condition room temperature, in refrigerator, and 40°C 75% RH and after specified duration it was observed that there were no sweating, bleeding, streaking and blooming.

Antifungal activity:

Anti-fungal activity of formulated lipstick was performed by zone of inhibition method using candida fungi. Reference standard (Curcumin+ DMSO), control sample (DMSO) and lipstick formulation were used to check the zone of inhibition. DMSO do not have antifungal properties, effect of DMSO on fungi was shown in petri plate C, formulation in B and Curcumin in A.

Petri plate A and B indicate zone of inhibition/antifungal activity of formulated herbal lipstick of Curcumin. As there was zone of inhibition seen are remarkable in both A and B petri plate, so it can be confirmed that formulated lipstick shows a good antifungal activity.

Fig.15: Antifungal Activity.

CONCLUSION

In the present work herbal lipstick containing Curcumin as antifungal agent and pomegranate arils extract coloring agent was formulated using beeswax, carnauba wax, cocoa butter, lanolin wax as natural ingredients. For selection of concentration of different ingredients preliminary trials was carried out. Different evaluation parameters were performed on the finalized formula which shows good shining, spreading and hardness and drug release. Systemic drug release was performed using cellophane membrane. Thus from the study it can be concluded that herbal lipstick could be promising drug delivery to cure lips fungal infection or angular cheilitis to achieve patient compliance.

'Bottom line'-

This research work could be further explored to develop the cosmeceuticals using the biologically active ingredients obtain from the herbal origin. By the addition of small amount of biologically active agents to the formulations, cosmeceutical formulation can be developed. These cosmeceuticals could be helpful to improve the skin, hair and nail fungal infection.

Abbreviations

Table 7: Abbreviations.

Abs.	Absorbance
Conc.	Concentration
pH	Hydrogen ion concentration
H	Hour
Min	Minute
g/ml	Gram per mole
mg	Microgram
ml	Milliliters
µg	Microgram
Mm	Micrometer
nm	Nanometer
MW	Molecular weight
°C	Degree Celsius
SD	Standard deviation
%	Percentage
µm	Micrometer
V	Volume
TPA	Texture Profile Analysis
UV	Ultraviolet
FT-IR	Fourier transform infrared
λ max	Maximum wavelength

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